

THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC AS A MOMENT OF RESURRECTION OF THE CREATIVE ECONOMY IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

A new problem in the field of health sciences in the form of the Covid-19 outbreak has an impact on other sectors, one of which is the economic sector. This research is a literature review approach. The impact of the emergence of the Covid-19 outbreak was felt by Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. Where Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises that contribute to the economy in the form of employment up to 97% have to rack their brains to survive in the midst of the Covid-19 pandemic. The main challenge that must be faced by Indonesia regarding the creative economy industry is related to the quality of human resources, capital and policies related to creative economy businesses. The Government of Indonesia through the ministry of tourism and creative economy as well as in collaboration with related parties provides various solutions to the problems faced by Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in every sub-sector of the creative economy industry. Various policies and activities were carried out to maintain the creative industry in the midst of the viciousness of the Covid-19 outbreak. Starting from providing operational funding assistance to registered Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, conducting training, to events in every sub-sector of the creative economy.

Keywords: covid19, pandemic, creative economy

Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic has actually been able to damage the economic structure of all countries in the world, including Indonesia. Almost all sectors are affected, starting from the economic sector, education, health and others (Andis Indrawan, Saputra, & Linawati, 2021). In essence, if in a country, one of the welcoming sectors is disturbed, then this will have an impact on other sectors. Just as in the era of the Covid-19 pandemic, an unseen outbreak can kill millions of human lives in Indonesia. The Covid-19 pandemic is one of the new problems in the health sector which is then able to affect all other sectors, one of which is the economic sector (Communications, 2021). Small, micro and medium enterprises are also feeling the impact of Covid-19. So that the government is trying as quickly as possible to provide various solutions to small, micro and medium enterprises in the form of financial assistance, tax cuts, training and other solutions.

The solution provided by the government is an effort so that Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises are able to survive in the midst of difficult conditions due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The government is willing to provide assistance of up to trillions of rupiah to be distributed to Micro, Small and Medium

Enterprises because Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises make a very large contribution to the national economy. This is evidenced by the fact that 117 million workers are absorbed by Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises or equivalent to 97% of the workforce absorption of the business world. In addition, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises are able to contribute as much as 61.1% to the national economy (GDP), and the rest comes from large business actors, namely 38.9%.

In addition to assistance in the form of funds, the government through the ministry of tourism and the creative economy which is now led by Mr. Sandiaga Uno has also made new breakthroughs to assist Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, one of which is by conducting various trainings in each sub-sector of the creative economy. There are 17 sub-sectors of the creative economy, namely game development, architecture, interior design, music, fine arts, product design, fashion, culinary, film, animation and video, photography, visual communication design, television and radio, crafts, advertising, performing arts, publishing and application.

The government through the ministry of tourism and creative economy encourages Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises to carry out various creations and innovations so that they are able to renew products and even create new products to have a higher selling value. Especially during this Covid-19 pandemic. People who experience layoffs must continue to earn income in various ways, one of which is by selling.

The digital era that requires everything to be done with the help of gadgets is also a business opportunity. For people who are digitally literate, they will use this opportunity as a source of income, because only with gadgets and quotas, as well as their ability to advertise, can sell other people's goods without having to spend extra money. However, not 100% of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises do marketing online due to limited knowledge about online marketing.

The Ministry of tourism and creative economy also plays an important role in improving the ability of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in marketing their superior products. One of them is by conducting digital marketing training in collaboration with various business platforms. In addition, the Ministry of tourism and creative economy also cooperates with local government ranks to explore or explore regional sectors that have great opportunities in national and even international markets, so that Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in the regions are able to create superior products from their respective regions which then able to compete in national and even international markets. Not only training that encourages finished products, but the Ministry of tourism and creative economy also provides training in all sub-sectors of the creative economy.

Unlike in the past, products that can be accepted in the community are only based on price and raw materials used. In today's era, creation and innovation as well as the ability to carry out promotions are the main provisions in conducting trading activities. One example is fashion products that come from organic and non-organic waste. It is innovation and creation that become the provisions of these business actors so that they are able to change waste that originally did not have a selling value to have a selling value. Not only that, there are still many new products that are loved by the public in the era of the covid-19 pandemic, one example of which is various home decoration products.

The Covid-19 problem faced by all countries in the world, including Indonesia and how the Indonesian government has taken various ways to deal with the impacts that have been caused, namely through the ministry of tourism and the creative economy to stabilize the economy as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic is a the phenomenon behind the researchers compiling a study entitled Pandemic Covid-19 as Momentum for the Awakening of the Creative Economy in Indonesia with the aim of examining how the government through various parties, one of which is through the ministry of tourism and the creative economy in collaboration with business actors of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises and other parties revive the creative economy in Indonesia in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Concept of Creativity

Creativity is defined in different ways (Tichy, 2001). There are so many different definitions, so the notion of creativity depends on how people define it - "*creativity is a matter of definition*" (Ajie, 1994).

The concept of creativity based on 3P (Widjaja & Winarso, 2019) :

- a. Process

Is a process that produces something new, and the creative process is the most important part in developing creativity. It can be interpreted to be busy creatively which shows the fluency of flexibility (flexibility) and originality in thinking and behaving.

b. Product

The definition of creativity based on the product is a creativity effort that focuses on the product or what is produced by individuals, either something new/original or an innovative elaboration/combination. A work can be said to be creative if it is a creation that is new or original and meaningful from the individual or to the environment.

c. Private

Creativity reflects the uniqueness of the individual in his thoughts and expressions. Creativity begins with the individual's ability to create something new (Istanto, 2015). A creative individual has an independent nature. He does not feel bound to the prevailing general values and norms.

Context of Creative Thinking

The most common definition of thinking is the development of ideas and concepts within a person. The development of these ideas and concepts takes place through the process of establishing relationships between parts of the information stored in a person in the form of notions. Thinking includes many mental activities. We think when we decide what to buy in the store. We think as we daydream while waiting for an introductory psychology course to begin. We think while trying to solve an exam given in class. We think when we write an article, write a paper, write a letter, read a book, read the newspaper, plan a vacation, or worry about a broken friendship.

In simple terms, thinking is processing information mentally or cognitively. More formally, thinking is the rearrangement or cognitive manipulation of both information from the environment and symbols stored in long term memory. So, thinking is a symbolic representation of some event or item (Khodijah, 2006: 117).

Thinking is a mental activity (Cahyono, 2016). The human thought process has two main characteristics (Hariyani, 2012), namely:

a. Covert / unobservable (not visible).

Thinking processes occur in the human brain and physically can not be seen the process (in terms of information processing) (Istanto, 2015). Some experts who have tried to physically monitor thought processes have only found weak electrical activity and chemical processes in the thinking human brain. Thus, the information processing process cannot be observed and seen physically or chemically. The processing of meaning, both semantic and visual, is abstract so that it cannot be detected by the five senses.

b. Symbolic (involves manipulation and use of symbols)

In thinking, humans process (manipulate) information in the form of symbols, (both verbal and visual symbols). The symbols will give meaning to the processed information.

The thought process is one of a series in the mechanism of interpretation of stimuli. In thinking all cognitive processes are involved, starting from sensation, perception and memory (Hariyani, 2012).

Broadly speaking, there are two kinds of ways of thinking, namely autistic thinking and realistic thinking (Mahmud, 2017). Autistic thinking is often referred to as daydreaming, daydreaming or fantasizing. With autistic thinking people escape from reality, seeing life as fantastic images.

On the other hand, realistic thinking is referred to as reasoning, namely thinking logically, based on existing facts and adjusting to the real world, along with all the arguments/laws.

Creativity is often thought of as a skill based on natural talent, where only those who are talented can be creative (Clear, 2015). This assumption is not entirely true, although in reality it appears that certain people have the ability to create new ideas quickly and easily. diverse.

Creative thinking has several mechanisms or processes that must be passed. According to David Cambell, there are five stages of creative thinking, including (Hariyani, 2012): Preparation, Concentration, Incubation, Illumination, Verification/ Production.

Creative thinking thrives when it is supported by internal and situational factors. Creative people have diverse temperaments (Akbar, Panuntun, & Asikin, 2021). Wagner was arrogant and controlling; Tchaikovsky is shy, quiet, and passive; Bryon is hypersexual; Newton was intolerant and short-tempered; Einstein was humble and simple. Nevertheless, there are three aspects that generally

characterize creative people according to Munandar (1999: 96); Cognitive ability, Open attitude, Attitude that is free, autonomous, and believe in yourself.

Innovation Concept

Innovation itself means introducing new ideas, new goods, new services and new ways that are more useful (Widjaja & Winarso, 2019). Innovation or innovation comes from the word to innovate which has the meaning of making changes or introducing something new (Amri & Ahmadi, 2010).

a. Product innovation

Involves the introduction of new goods, substantially improved new services. And also an increase in function characteristics, technician abilities, and ease of use (Anjaningrum & Sidi, 2018). For example: cell phones, computers, etc.

b. Educational innovation

Innovation also applies in the world of education (Hains & Hains, 2020). A clear example of innovation in the world of education is the application of an anti-corruption curriculum in schools. This curriculum certainly did not exist when Indonesia became independent in 1945. Along with the times, innovation in the curriculum was felt to be necessary. One example is the inclusion of anti-corruption education (Wahyudin & Susilana, 2011).

c. Public service innovation

Previously, public services could only be done face-to-face. However, with the development of current technology, public services can be done online (Octaleny, 2020).

d. Technological innovation

Innovation in the field of technology is currently developing very rapidly, which makes humans able to interact with anyone without limits. This is evidenced by the existence of various kinds of social media such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram that reach users all over the world (Periyadi, Sri Bulkia, 2020).

e. Cultural innovation

Culture is closely related to the life of the nation. Innovations in the cultural field can be in the form of cultural festivals or other festivals, for example the batik festival (Mansur, Taufik, & Nurmaeta, 2020).

The reason humans have to be creative and innovative

Creativity can be done by anyone who wants. According to Colin Rose & Malcolm J. Nichol (2002: 275) in their book *Accelerated Learning*, "Being creative is not just sitting around waiting for a flash of inspiration. Creativity demands a lot of hard work and requires careful preparation." Especially now that many people write *Ways to be creative*, whether in the form of literature, games, thought maps, etc. Therefore, creativity development is carried out from an early age (Budiarti, 2015), reviews and studies on the creative process, its conditions and ways that can foster, stimulate, and develop it are very important.

Some reasons why creativity needs to be nurtured from an early age:

a. By being creative, people can actualize (actualize) themselves, and self-actualization is a basic need at the highest level in human life (Maslow, 1967). Creativity is a manifestation of a fully functioning individual.

b. Creativity or creative thinking as the ability to see various possible solutions to a problem is a form of thinking that until now has received little attention in education (Guilford, 1967).

c. Being creatively busy is not only beneficial (for the individual and for the environment) but also gives satisfaction to the individual.

d. Creativity enables humans to improve their quality of life.

Creativity and Innovation in the economic field in Indonesia

The creative industry itself is actually a concept that has emerged before the emergence of the concept of the creative economy. The term "creative industry" was recorded in 1994 in the "Creative Nation" report issued by Australia. However, this term really started to lift in 1997 when the United Kingdom Department of Culture, Media, and Sport (DCMS) established the Creative Industries Task Force.

This definition of Creative Industries Task Force is the reference for the definition of creative industries in Indonesia as written in the 2009-2015 Indonesian Creative Economy Development Plan Book issued by the Ministry of Trade of the Republic of Indonesia (2008) as follows: individuals to create prosperity and employment through the creation and utilization of the creative power and creativity of the individual. To date, the Government of Indonesia itself has identified the scope of the creative industry covering 15 sub-sectors (Purnomo, 2016) including; Advertising, Architecture, Art Market, Craft, Design, Fashion, Video, Film and Photography, Interactive Games, Music, Performing Arts, Publishing and Printing, Computer Services and Software or Information Technology, Television & Radio (broadcasting), Research and Development and Culinary.

The role of the government in dealing with economic problems due to the COVID-19 pandemic through the Creative Economy

The government, through the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy (Susanti & Syahar, 2019), has made various efforts to overcome the problems caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. Some of these things are by conducting various events or events and then training in all sub-sectors of the creative economy.

Events or events and training held by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy to support the Indonesian economy in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic (RI, 2021a).

a. Holding Modest Fashion Funders Fund 2021

The Modest Fashion Funders Fund 2021 program implemented by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy in Jakarta on February 23, 2021 with the aim of assisting modest fashion brands in developing business, increasing capacity and related to access to capital. The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy is trying to prepare Modest Fashion founders to be able to improve their business management. This is done because the fashion subsector in the creative economy is able to make a significant contribution because fashion is always evolving, and Indonesian people, especially fashion customers, are very fast in following fashion changes (Rahayu, 2021a).

The Modest Fashion Funders Fund 2021 program prepares participants to be ready to be ogled by investors both from outside and from within the country who are certainly potential and ready to be looked at by institutions related to funding. This program collaborates with various parties, especially mentors from the fields of fashion, finance, digital marketing, financial institutions (banks) and venture capital.

b. Charisma Event Nusantara

Charisma Event Nusantara is a program implemented by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy in collaboration with local governments to improve the tourism sector and the creative economy of every region in Indonesia. The diversity of various tribes, traditions, cultures, and culinary arts in each region in Indonesia creates its own uniqueness, so the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy sees it as an opportunity to introduce the tourism sector and potential products from each region to local and foreign communities (RI, 2021c).

c. *NGOPREK*(Chat with Creative Economy)

The Covid-19 pandemic has in fact been able to cause business actors in the creative economy sector to be distraught, especially in terms of financial turnover. In fact, in 2019, the creative economy sector was able to absorb 17 million workers. Therefore, the government must take part in the problems faced by business actors in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. The government through the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy provides facilities to business actors in the creative economy sector in the form of a program called *NGOPREK*(Creative Economy Chat Together) (RI, 2021b).

Ngoprek is a facility where business actors in the creative economy sector can describe all their problems and complaints in dealing with economic problems to the Government, through the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy. So that the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy is able to clearly identify the problems that are being faced. Furthermore, with the ngoprek program, the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy and business actors who then work together with related parties are able to formulate various joint solutions related to the problems being faced.

d. Lake Toba Creative Buying Movement

The Lake Toba Creative Buying Movement will be held on February 21, 2021, which is a follow-up to the "Proud of Indonesia" national movement. The purpose of holding the Lake Toba Creative Buying

Movement is to explore the potential for tourism and the creative economy in the Lake Toba area which is one of the destinations that is a priority scale out of a total of 5 main priorities. In addition, the government through the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy also provides assistance and education to creative economy business actors to develop and advance their business with e-commerce platforms. The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy also encourages the craftsmen of Kampung Ulos from North Sumatra to increase innovation and creation in order to be able to increase production so that the income generated also increases and of course penetrates the international market.

e. Discuss the Capital Market with Tourism and Creative Economy Players in Surabaya

The capital market talk show with tourism and creative industry players will be held on February 19, 2021 in Surabaya. This activity aims to introduce entrepreneurs, especially Micro, Small And Medium Business players, about access to financing using the stock exchange through Initial Public Offering. Capital is a major problem for business actors. As many as 92.37% of creative economy actors get capital from their own savings, family loans because of the difficulty of getting loans from financial institutions. Of all creative economic entrepreneurs, 24.44% managed to get financing through financial institutions, and 0.66% from non-banking financial institutions (Rahayu, 2021d).

With the capital market talk show, the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy hopes that business actors can share experiences in obtaining business capital, one of which is through the capital market. The first step taken by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy is to introduce the capital market.

f. Adian Nalambok Spot Renovation

The Nalambok adian spot is located on the back of a hill between Parapat to Balige, Tampahan sub-district, Toba Samosir Regency. Adian Nalambok spot is a spot that is able to provide views of the beauty of Lake Toba from above. The purpose of the renovation of the Adian Nalambok spot is to restore the tourism sector and the creative economy in the area. So that it can absorb more workers (Rahayu, 2021c).

g. Socialization of FoodStarup Indonesia

The socialization of Indonesian foodstartip was held on February 17, 2021 in Malang, East Java. This activity is carried out online and offline through the Zoom application. The purpose of holding this socialization is so that culinary business actors are able to grow and continue to develop amid the COVID-19 pandemic and build a culinary industry ecosystem by connecting it to access to financing or capital, so that culinary business actors are not constrained by costs or capital when they need it. In addition, the participants were given knowledge and understanding on how to get access to capital through the FSI program. The participants also gained knowledge about marketing and product distribution.

h. Support the 2021 banyuwangi festival

Banyuwangi festival in 2021 is an annual routine activity that presents 102 events from various kinds of attractions. The banyuwangi festival in 2021 will be carried out offline and online with a colorful hybrid concept. This activity aims to make the community's creativity run even though in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. This activity is also able to increase the economy of the Banyuwangi Regency, this is proven in 2019 PAD increased by Rp. 29 billion, the poverty rate decreased to 7.52%, GRDP increased by 157.5% and per capita income increased by 149%. With evidence of an increase in the economy in 2019, this festival activity will still be carried out with a new concept in the new normal era so that it can provide a new sensation as well (Rahayu, 2021b).

i. Strengthen cooperation with Hungary

Hungarian tourists contribute quite a lot to the Indonesian tourism sector. However, since the Covid-19 outbreak, at the beginning of 2019 there were 12,218 recorded visits to Indonesia. However, in 2020 the number experienced a drastic decline, namely 3,559 tourists. The decline in the number of tourists from Hungary is the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic because there are many policies from each country, both Indonesia and Hungary, in responding to this Covid-19 outbreak. Responding to this problem, the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy will increase tourism promotion as has been carried out before, namely fam-trips, sales missions as well as various festivals and exhibitions with the aim of increasing the number of foreign tourists to visit Indonesian tourist destinations.

Minister of Tourism and Creative Economy, Sandiaga Salahudin Uno also increased cooperation with Hungary in the creative economy, especially in the field of information technology and start-ups. The

Covid-19 pandemic is able to have an impact on the rapid development of information technology, so that the Indonesian people, especially creative economy players in the field of information technology, must be able to develop quickly.

j. BEKUP (Baparekraf For Startup)

Baparekraf For Startup Program is a forum to support start-ups in the creative industry by providing intensive assistance to be able to survive, especially in the midst of a pandemic and continue to develop rapidly.

Actually, there are still many activities carried out by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy which aim to maintain, improve and create businesses in the creative economy in Indonesia.

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